

IMPROVED ROCK ANCHORS

Synopsis: when we construct any structure on black cotton soil (expansive soil) or in the area where water level is higher than foundation level, the base of the structure is subjected to high uplift force leading to cracking in the floor or other members of the structure. Keeping long discussion short ground anchors are one of the alternatives to overcome the uplift force acting under the structure. There are different types of anchors used now days.

Here I got a chance to visit a site where ground or rock anchors were being used. These anchors (mild steel tendons) were 10 m in length out of which 5m was the length of the part to be stressed and rest 5m was for forming the bond with the hard strata.

For installing those boreholes were drilled up to a depth of 10 m and then the tendons were inserted in the bore holes and grouted. And it was locked at the top and post tensioned after the curing of the grout is done. It is very effective method. This is done at regular spacing as per the design requirement.

I was little concern about the 5m length of tendons which was being used for forming bond with the hard strata, and the digging of the extra depth when it can be done with much less efforts and efficiently. This can be done by providing anchor as used by ships to halt or warriors to climb the castles.

For its easy installation in larger depths, we can make our anchor portable. This can be spread into its original shape after it has been placed in the required depth.

Basic concept:

This anchor is having four arms. Initially it looks like a metal cylinder and can be placed in the bored holes. After it reaches the required depth, the base of the anchor will rest on the surface. Then we will insert a metal cylinder as shown in the diagram to proceed with ramming and transferring the thrust so as to open the anchor arms. We have a locking system for the anchor once the arms are fully opened.

Materials required:

(12-20mm diameter) tendons (generally they are used in sets of three, it can also vary as per design requirements), mild steel fabricated anchor, cement grout, couplers, metallic cylinder (outer diameter 20mm less than the drilled hole diameter and inner diameter of cylinder 10 mm more than the diameter of the plastic duct which is having the tendons within).

Machines required:

Driller, rammer, grout injector, hydraulic jack for post tensioning

Working:

First we have to drill hole of 5 m at regular interval (the depth and interval between the anchors may vary depending on the properties of the strata). The diameter of the drilled holes also varies from 100mm to 200 mm depending on the local conditions.

Then the anchor attached with mild steel tendons is inserted in the holes. The mild steel tendons are covered with a plastic sheet so as to avoid direct contact with the grout. The tendons are provided solely for taking care of the tension generated.

Initially the tendons are placed along with a metallic cylinder surrounding it. This cylinder is provided to transfer the thrust of ramming to the anchor which will be placed at some depth. After the ramming is done and the anchor is locked by the locking system 2 (which is explained below) the metallic cylinder is removed and used for ramming other anchors.

When the anchor reaches the bottom of the drilled hole, the ramming is done on the metal cylinder. This cylinder transfers the thrust to the anchor at the bottom. This anchor is designed in such a way that it expands its arms in the hard strata; penetration of arms in the strata is facilitated by the sharp edge of the arms, the hardness of the arm material and the thrust applied by ramming. This is shown in diagram 1.

The anchor is having a tapered metal cylinder of 1 feet passing through the anchor. The tapered cylinder has openings along its length close to the wider end. It is shown in diagram 2. When the anchor moves down due to ramming, the expanded cylindrical mouth contracts due to the downward movement of anchor. As soon as the anchor passes the mouth of the cylinder, it regains its shape by expanding. This leads to locking of the anchor, by restricting its upward motion and closing of the anchor arms.

After the anchor is locked, the cylinder which was placed for ramming should be removed and used for other anchors.

Then post tensioning should be done followed by grouting.

Advantage:

1. Saves a lot of material
2. Saves time of drilling, since have to drill half the depth of what was done earlier.
3. We don't have to wait for drying of the first section of grouting, which is to form the bond with the strata and the entangled tendons before post tensioning. It saves a lot of time.

Disadvantage:

1. We have to hire a rammer along with the driller.(but the net time and cost saved is much more than what is put into it).

Diagram 1

Note: Dimensions not to scale

Diagram 2

Locking system for the anchor

Note: Dimensions not to scale